

Speculation on Radiation from a Moving Charge

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Maxwell's equations applied to an accelerating charge lead to the prediction of emitted radiation through a nonvanishing Poynting surface integral for a large radius. The result depends on sources, i.e. charge and current densities, acting as functions of $t-R/c$ while $E(r,t)$ and $B(r,t)$. Φ and A , electric and magnetic potentials depend on charge and current sources, q and q velocity for a point charge. $-\text{grad } \Phi$ (which is identical to $-\text{grad } V(r)$ for other potentials), acting on a function of $t-R/c$, say $v(t-R/c)$ from $\Phi(r,t)$ yields a term behaving as: $d/dr q v(t-R/c) = d/dt q v(t-R/c) (1/c)$ or in other words acceleration appears and $-\text{grad}$ does not act on $1/r$ in the denominator of $\Phi(r,t-R/c)$. As a result, a term with acceleration has a slow dropping r dependence in E allowing for the surface integral of the Poynting vector to be non-vanishing and for radiation to be emitted.

In this note, we investigate whether this result may be anticipated in a different manner. We note that the electric potential Φ depends directly on the charge source. A second point charge has a potential energy of $q_1 \Phi(r,t)$ which should increase its mass by this amount. Thus, given a point charge q , it not only has self-energy, but gives potential energy to another charge, affecting that charge's mass. If the first charge q is accelerated, this means one has ma , but the extra "mass" $q_1 \Phi$ should also accelerate as $q_1 \Phi a$ as it is a mass in the system. This predicts a term $q_1 \Phi a$ which is equivalent to force i.e. contributes to the electric field from q . Thus, Φ should have a term of the form of $\text{velocity}/r$. In calculating E , one term is $-\text{grad } \Phi$ (the other is dA/dt) so $-\text{grad } \Phi(r)$ should yield a term with a (acceleration) leading to the idea of $t-r/c$ for the time of the source. Φ , however, drops as $1/r$ and so this E field term drops very slowly with r . We argue this is equivalent to radiation being emitted as it is so different from the $1/(r^2)$ behaviour of E (which appears in different terms). We thus argue that one may anticipate radiation emission by an accelerating charge without the use of Maxwell's equations, although using the Poynting vector surface integral (which follows from Maxwell's equations) is very useful in showing outgoing EM momentum i.e. radiation.

Maxwell's Equations

Maxwell's equations without sources give rise to an equation for the photon as shown by Maxwell. In addition, they give rise to radiation emission from an accelerating charge. Two features are used to demonstrate this (1). First, the time in sources is given as $t-r/c$ and not t , even though $\Phi(r,t)$, $A(r,t)$, $E(r,t)$ and $B(r,t)$. Thus, the effects of a source moving with velocity v at time t_1 are felt at a later time in the EM fields. Secondly, one may use Maxwell's equations to write the continuity equation:

$$d/dt(\text{partial}) .5(\epsilon_0 E E + 1/\mu_0 B B) = \text{grad} . [1/\mu_0 E \times B] \quad ((1))$$

((1)) may be integrated over volume and the quantity on the RHS converted to:

Integral $dA \cdot \mathbf{E}$ (normal to surface) ((2))

If one considers a sphere with a radius tending to infinite and ((2)) does not vanish, it suggests that radiation is emitted (accounting for the EM momentum flux). This is of relevance because it is exactly what occurs in the case of an accelerating charge (or charge distribution).

In order to calculate radiation from an accelerating charge, it seems one must make the a priori assumption that EM quantities (ϕ , A , E , B) at a point r feel the effects of a source at time t at a later time, in particular, in (1) it is suggested that there is a delay of R/c , the time taken by a signal leaving the source and travelling a distance of R to the point of measurement of the EM quantity.

Specifically, one may calculate $\phi(r,t)$ and $A(r,t)$ electric and magnetic potentials respectively. Full details are given in (1), Here, we only focus on how one term from $\phi(r,t)$ leads to a term in the electric field E which behaves as (q/r) where a is acceleration of the charge. (Other terms of the same order appear in a full calculation, but this one term establishes a nonvanishing Poynting contribution ((2)) (assuming the various terms of this order do not cancel, which they do not).

$\phi(r,t) = 1/(4\pi\epsilon_0) \int \text{density}(r_1, t-R/c) / R$ where:

$R = \text{magnitude}|r-r_1|$ where r is the distance vector from an origin to the EM measuring point and r_1 is the distance from the origin to the charge. Then,

R approx equal to $r - r_1 \cdot r / r$ and density may be expanded in a Taylor series yielding one term proportional to velocity of order $1/r$. Thus:

$\phi(r,t)$ has a term $1/(4\pi\epsilon_0) \int \text{qr} \cdot v / (rr)$ ((3))

$E = -\text{grad} \phi + dA/dt$ ((4)) so ((3)) yields a contribution of a term $1/(4\pi\epsilon_0) (-\text{grad} \cdot v/(rr))$

Grad operates on both $1/r$ and $v(t-r/c)$. [Note: Originally one had $\text{density}(r_1, t-R/c)$, but a Taylor expansion leads to $\text{density}(r_1, t-r/c)$ as a leading term.] Thus, one of the terms involves grad operating on $v(t-r/c)$ leaving $1/r$ untouched. This leads to a very slowly dropping term of the electric field E . (For a charge at rest, E drops as $1/(rr)$.)

As a result, after a full calculation is performed in (1), one finds $1/\mu_0 \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ along r to have a term proportional to $[aa]$, where a is acceleration (Larmor's result) and $1/(rr)$. This cancels with $4\pi\epsilon_0 rr$ from the surface area leading to EM contributions as r goes to infinite, or radiation emission.

Idea of Acceleration

In this note, we investigate whether the idea of E having a term proportional to a/r follows without the use of Maxwell's equations. It is often argued that a static charge may be built by

adding spherical shells, one on top of the other. Work is done fighting the electrostatic repulsion which appears as self-energy density $\frac{1}{2}\epsilon_0 E^2$.

Similarly, if a second charge q_1 is brought near the first, it has a potential energy of:

$Q_1 \phi(r,t)$ where $\phi(r,t)$ is the electrostatic potential from q which is taken to be static i.e. q/r ((4))

For the case in which q accelerates, there should be a term ma related to force. If one considers q_1 to be part of the system, one might expect to see its potential energy (related to mass by $E=mc^2$) also accelerate i.e. one might expect a term of:

$Q_1 \phi(r,t) a$ ((5)) where $\phi(r,t) = q/r$

This term is related to force and so should appear as a term in E , the electric field. Although this argument is hand-wavy, it seems one should expect a term in the electric field which drops as $1/r$ and is proportional to acceleration. An electric field associated with a static charge (and even ones moving at constant velocity) drops much faster, thus it seems there is the possibility for EM energy to become disassociated from an accelerating charge. (In a more formal sense, one should calculate the surface integral of the Poynting vector (normal to the surface), but this involves use of Maxwell's equations (i.e. the Poynting vector follows from Maxwell's equations).

If one expects a term like ((5)) in E , then it should follow from $-\text{grad } \phi(r,t)$. This seems to lead to the idea of density $(r, t-R/c)$ i.e. an EM measurement at r,t depends on the source at $r, t-R/c$. For $R=r$ to first order, this allows $-\text{grad } \phi(r,t)$ to operate on $v(t-r/c)$ to yield an acceleration term. One may note that in this scenario, the use of $t-R/c$ does not appear a priori. It follows from ((5)) which is linked to Newton's law applied to electrostatic energy/mass.

Conclusion

It is well-known that Maxwell's equations for an accelerating charge lead to radiation emission given by Larmor's equation (1). The calculation uses the a priori idea that contributions to EM quantities such as ϕ , A , E and B at (r,t) are due to sources at $t-R/c$ where R is the distance from the source to the point of measurement. This leads to a term in ϕ for an accelerating charge proportional to $q v(t-r/c)/r$ to first order. This term is of the same order as q/r , but taking $-\text{grad}$ yields two terms. The first acts on $v(t-r/c)$ creating $a(t-r/c)q/r$ so there is a contribution to E , electric field, of the order qa/r . This term drops very slowly with r and may be shown to create radiation emission (together with other similar terms) when calculating the surface area of the normal component of the Poynting vector.

In this note, we argue that one may anticipate a term qa/r in the electric field without use of Maxwell's equations. We argue that $q_1 q/r$ is the electrostatic potential (or extra mass $E=mc^2$) for a charge q_1 in the presence of a static charge q . If there is acceleration a , one expects ma throughout, so the extra mass of q_1 (electromagnetic mass) should appear as aq/r where a is acceleration. This term should be related to force i.e. to a term in the electric field so there is a

very slowly dropping aq/r term in E for an accelerating q . $E = -\text{grad } \phi + dA/dt$ so one may anticipate a term in $\phi(r,t)$ of $qv(t-R/c)/r$ where R is the distance from the point charge to the measuring point. Thus, one introduces the idea of two different times, a signal time $t-R/c$ from the source and a time t when the signal arrives at R . This allows $-\text{grad}$ to act on $v(t-R/c)$ which is approximately equal to $v(t-r/c)$ to first order. This leads to $-\text{grad } v(t-r/c) = dv/dt \cdot 1/c$ or acceleration, leaving $1/r$ in the denominator untouched. (This is only one term of this order in the calculation. One must also calculate the magnetic potential A and then B in order to find the Poynting vector, but we consider this one term as an example.)

The E term aq/r drops much more slowly than the usual electrostatic $q/(rr)$ and so one may postulate that the aq/r portion of E is no longer part of the charge q . (More formally, one would use the surface integral of the normal of the Poynting vector), but it seems there should be simple reason that E (which is like a force to a charge q_1) has a leading term a $[\phi \text{ static}]$ with ϕ static being like an "em mass" portion to the charge q_1 .

References

1. Reitz, J. and Milford, F. and Christy, R. Foundations of Electromagnetic Theory (Addison Wesley 1980)